

North Ridge Project, Ottawa County

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient benefit of the North Ridge Project has been stewarded by the private property owner actively managing the water level control structures (WLCSs) at the Project. Communication mechanisms for tracking WLCS changes improved in 2024 in order to prepare for an estimate of surface water nutrient filtration. For now, researchers estimate that this Project’s runoff prevention conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source also prevents approximately 0.7 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is actively managed. This Project has 23 acres of restored wetland consisting of three wetland pools: Center, East, and West. Water inputs come from tile drainage in the farm field to the north flowing into the “L” shaped ditch around the wetland site. The pump at the southern point of the ditch pumps ditch water into the wetland pools. Water outflows from the Project through a WLCS to Packer Creek. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a pumping event where water is actively pumped from the drainage ditch into the wetland pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Total Phosphorus Runoff Prevention	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
23 acres	0.7 lbs	20 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement

Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar actively managed and/or formerly agricultural wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Create pump infrastructure and plan active management that balances water input volumes with residence time to maximize nutrient input and filtration potential.
- Assess parcels for consistent connection to nutrient-laden water inputs (e.g., tile drainage) to maintain consistent opportunity for nutrient retention.

Improved understanding of nutrient retention at this Project will rely on sampling during hydrologic events and collecting data on measurement of flow through the agricultural pump, requiring timely notification of pump actions. These efforts are supported by iteratively improving open communication between property managers and researchers.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.